

MEANS OF EXPRESSION OF WISH CATEGORY IN ENGLISH

Kaipova D.B

Master's degree student.

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

Abstract: *the article deals with the notion of modality and identifies the means of Wish category of English language. There given semantic meanings of “wish” expressions. There are fulfilled and unfulfilled wishes.*

Keywords: *wish, meaning of modality, main and auxiliary verbs, reality /irreality.*

Inrtoduction

The notion modality has an important impact on language. Many expressions in our lives are related to modality. The study of modality is called ‘Tropology’. The first man to introduce the notion "modality" into science was Aristotle. Sh. Bally says: "Modality is a heart and soul of the sentence". Modality is a category of linguistics which expresses the speaker's/writer's attitudes (*mode of reassurance, possibility, obligation, necessity, prediction, willingness, permission, volition, ability*), or how the speaker or writer feels about a state or event. Modal verbs are the main carriers of modality.

The studies on the concept of modality have been investigated and developed by V.V.Vinogradov, Galperin, M.A.Blokh, Erhart, Jespersen, F.R.Palmer, I.B.Morozova, Lewis, Sh.Ballie, Coates. Palmer argues that “Modals are important and at the same time are difficult area in English grammar” (1979, Preface) He defines that modals and modality are inseparable.

A number of scholars have assumed wish as the meaning of modality and have made attempts to prove this thesis. (Ballie, 1955; Bogdanov, 1977) Some scholars determine modality parameters as: the attitude of the speaker to the situation and the

status of the situation concerning reality /irreality. The latter model appeared to be one of the functional theories of diachronic morphology. In this case wish is affirmed. We come to the conclusion that the verbs denoting "wish" can express the modality by the enumerated sema beginning from strong wish to the weaker one. Wish means of expression are given below:

Means	Explanation	Examples
1. <u>MAIN VERBS</u>	<p><i>Wish</i>-refer to past, present or future</p> <p><i>Hope</i>- is mainly used in wishes. .</p> <p><i>Want</i>- informal, expresses a wish, fulfilled and unfulfilled</p> <p><i>Like</i>- a wish about a future situation</p> <p><i>Prefer</i>- express a wish in relation to present, future or past.</p> <p><i>Love</i>- express fulfilled wishes</p>	<p>I wish I were there(present)</p> <p>I hope Hugh has apologized</p> <p>We wanted to establish peace.</p> <p>He would like to talk</p> <p>They would prefer to vote</p> <p>I would love to sail if I could afford it</p>
2. <u>AUXILIARY VERBS</u>	<p><i>May</i>-express fulfilled present and future wishes</p> <p><i>Had</i>- express unfulfilled wishes, used in inversion.</p> <p><i>Were</i>- express unfulfilled wishes that refer to present</p> <p><i>Might</i>-express unfulfilled wishes referring to past and present. It's used in inversion.</p> <p><i>Could</i>-expresses fulfilled wishes related to present. It implies that what is wished is not and never will be attained: “</p> <p><i>Would</i>- expresses fulfilled and unfulfilled wishes and refers to past, present and future.</p> <p><i>Will</i>- expresses fulfilled wishes related to present and future.</p>	<p>May she rest in peace</p> <p>Had I but taken your advice!</p> <p>O were he only here!</p> <p>Might he come in time!</p> <p>O, could you only go ahead!</p> <p>Would that everyone treated me considerately!</p> <p>Will you post this letter for me?“(request)</p>
3. <u>INVOCATION</u>	Wishing the addressee good by invoking God, The Lord or Heaven	The Lord bless him!
4. <u>IMPRECATION</u>	The speaker wishes that God or Heaven would do smth bad to the addressee	The devil take you

<u>5.</u> THE PASSIVE	Fulfilled wishes referring to present/future; followed by the verb “be” and the subject:	<i>God be praised</i> <i>Blessed be God!</i>
<u>6.</u> IMPERATIVE-	Fulfilled wishes ;refer to present/future. Three forms: a. Verb + complementation, b. please, c. let.	a. Be happy! Have a nice journey! b. Please, be thinking about me. c. Let us proceed!
<u>7.</u> SUBORDINATE CLAUSES-	Wishes are unfulfilled; refer to past, formed by if and that	If it were only true! If only I could swim!
<u>8.</u> INTERJECTIONAL FORMS	Followed by infinitive clause/prepositional phrases.	<i>Oh to be rich!</i> <i>Oh to see them</i>
<u>9.</u> STEREOTYPED PHRASES	These are six phrases: ➤ it is time ➤ would rather ➤ heaven forbid ➤ suffice it to say ➤ far be it from ➤ woe betide	It’s time to go home I’d rather you had told me about it Heaven forbid he should suffer Suffice it to say we won Far be it from her to settle it Woe betide the founders.
<u>10.</u> FOSSILISED WISHES	They include congratulations (Happy New Year, Happy Birthday), felicitations (Good luck.), invocations and greetings (Good morning.)	Fossilised wishes are fulfilled due to their reference to future.
<u>11.</u> MISCELLANEOUS TYPES OF WISHES	Miscellaneous types of wishes are all wishes that vary in form. In general, these wishes are fulfilled and refer to future. First, elliptical forms are used. In these forms , a verb like wish, hope or may is deleted, this is since the wish is for certain addressee with whom the speaker is familiar (I or We hope, wish)	➤ More power to your elbows! ➤ My warm regards. ➤ Peace and rest.

Conclusion

Modality is closely connected to our everyday lives. Modality is the attitude of a speaker to the utterance. In linguistics the grammatical category that is all about how we express our wants, wishes, and desires is called optative modality. The category of

wish has eleven means of expression which have their significant roles in linguistics. There are fulfilled and unfulfilled wishes according to their reference to past, present and future. The concept Wish is one of categories of modality which expresses the speaker's attitudes *of willingness or volition*. And the means of expression of wish can vary starting from main verbs to miscellaneous types of wishes.

References:

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